

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 86

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 86

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 86:0 A Prayer of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 86:1 תִּפְלֵה לְדָוִד הַטֹּה־יְהוָה</p>
<p>Psa. 86:1 "Incline Your ear, O LORD, and answer me;</p>	<p>אֲזַנְךָ עָנֵנִי כִי־עָנִי וְאֶבְיוֹן אָנִי : 2</p>
<p>For I am ^bafflicted and needy.</p>	<p>שָׁמְרָה נַפְשִׁי כִי־חָסִיד אָנִי הוֹשַׁע</p>
<p>² "Preserve my ¹soul, for I am a ^bgodly man;</p>	<p>עֲבֹדְךָ אַתָּה אֱלֹהֵי הַבּוֹטְחִים אֵלֶיךָ : תִּגְנֵנִי אֲדֹנָי כִּי אֵלֶיךָ אֶקְרָא כָּל־</p>
<p>O You my God, save Your servant who ^ctrusts in You.</p>	<p>הַיּוֹם : 4 שְׁמַחַת נַפְשׁ עֲבֹדְךָ כִּי אֵלֶיךָ</p>
<p>³ Be ^agracious to me, O Lord, For ^bto You I cry all day long.</p>	<p>אֲדֹנָי נַפְשִׁי אֲשָׂא : 5 כִּי־אַתָּה אֲדֹנָי</p>
<p>⁴ Make glad the soul of Your servant, For to You, O Lord, ^dI lift up my soul.</p>	<p>טוֹב וְסִלַּח וְרַב־חֶסֶד לְכֹל־ קְרָאֶיךָ : 6 הֶאֱזִינָה יְהוָה תִּפְלֵתִי</p>
<p>⁵ For You, Lord, are ^agood, and ^bready to forgive, And ^cabundant in lovingkindness to all who call upon You.</p>	<p>וְהִקְשִׁיבָה בְּקוֹל תַּחֲנוּנֹתַי : 7 בְּיוֹם צָרָתִי אֶקְרָאֶךָ כִּי תִעַנְנֵנִי : 8 אִי־כַמוֹךָ בְּאֱלֹהִים אֲדֹנָי וְאִי־כַמֶּעֲשִׂיךָ : 9 כָּל־גּוֹיִם אֲשֶׁר עָשִׂיתָ יְבוֹאוּ וַיִּשְׁתַּחֲוּוּ לְפָנֶיךָ אֲדֹנָי וַיִּכְבְּדוּ לְשִׁמְךָ : 10 כִּי־גָדוֹל אַתָּה וְעָשִׂיתָ נִפְלְאוֹת אַתָּה אֱלֹהִים לְבַדְּךָ : 11 הוֹרַנִי יְהוָה וַדַּרְכְּךָ אֶתְהַלֵּךְ בְּאַמְתָּךָ יַתֵּד לְבָבִי לִירְאָה שִׁמְךָ : 12 אֲדֹנָי אֱלֹהֵי בְּכֹל־לְבָבִי וְאֶכְבְּדָה שִׁמְךָ לְעוֹלָם : 13 כִּי־חָסִידְךָ גָּדוֹל עָלַי וְהִצַּלְתָּ נַפְשִׁי מִשָּׂאוֹל תַּחֲתִיתָ : 14 אֱלֹהִים אֲדָרִים קָמוּ־עָלַי וְעַתָּה עֲרִיצִים בְּקִשְׁוֹ נַפְשִׁי וְלֹא שָׁמַדְךָ לְיַגְדָּם : 15 וְאַתָּה</p>
<p>⁵ For You, Lord, are ^agood, and ^bready to forgive, And ^cabundant in lovingkindness to all who call upon You.</p>	<p>יְבוֹאוּ וַיִּשְׁתַּחֲוּוּ לְפָנֶיךָ אֲדֹנָי וַיִּכְבְּדוּ לְשִׁמְךָ : 10 כִּי־גָדוֹל אַתָּה וְעָשִׂיתָ נִפְלְאוֹת אַתָּה אֱלֹהִים לְבַדְּךָ : 11 הוֹרַנִי יְהוָה וַדַּרְכְּךָ אֶתְהַלֵּךְ בְּאַמְתָּךָ יַתֵּד לְבָבִי לִירְאָה שִׁמְךָ : 12 אֲדֹנָי אֱלֹהֵי בְּכֹל־לְבָבִי וְאֶכְבְּדָה שִׁמְךָ לְעוֹלָם : 13 כִּי־חָסִידְךָ גָּדוֹל עָלַי וְהִצַּלְתָּ נַפְשִׁי מִשָּׂאוֹל תַּחֲתִיתָ : 14 אֱלֹהִים אֲדָרִים קָמוּ־עָלַי וְעַתָּה עֲרִיצִים בְּקִשְׁוֹ נַפְשִׁי וְלֹא שָׁמַדְךָ לְיַגְדָּם : 15 וְאַתָּה</p>
<p>⁶ "Give ear, O LORD, to my prayer; And give heed to the voice of my supplications!</p>	<p>יְבוֹאוּ וַיִּשְׁתַּחֲוּוּ לְפָנֶיךָ אֲדֹנָי וַיִּכְבְּדוּ לְשִׁמְךָ : 10 כִּי־גָדוֹל אַתָּה וְעָשִׂיתָ נִפְלְאוֹת אַתָּה אֱלֹהִים לְבַדְּךָ : 11 הוֹרַנִי יְהוָה וַדַּרְכְּךָ אֶתְהַלֵּךְ בְּאַמְתָּךָ יַתֵּד לְבָבִי לִירְאָה שִׁמְךָ : 12 אֲדֹנָי אֱלֹהֵי בְּכֹל־לְבָבִי וְאֶכְבְּדָה שִׁמְךָ לְעוֹלָם : 13 כִּי־חָסִידְךָ גָּדוֹל עָלַי וְהִצַּלְתָּ נַפְשִׁי מִשָּׂאוֹל תַּחֲתִיתָ : 14 אֱלֹהִים אֲדָרִים קָמוּ־עָלַי וְעַתָּה עֲרִיצִים בְּקִשְׁוֹ נַפְשִׁי וְלֹא שָׁמַדְךָ לְיַגְדָּם : 15 וְאַתָּה</p>
<p>⁷ In ^athe day of my trouble I shall call upon You, For ^bYou will answer me.</p>	<p>יְבוֹאוּ וַיִּשְׁתַּחֲוּוּ לְפָנֶיךָ אֲדֹנָי וַיִּכְבְּדוּ לְשִׁמְךָ : 10 כִּי־גָדוֹל אַתָּה וְעָשִׂיתָ נִפְלְאוֹת אַתָּה אֱלֹהִים לְבַדְּךָ : 11 הוֹרַנִי יְהוָה וַדַּרְכְּךָ אֶתְהַלֵּךְ בְּאַמְתָּךָ יַתֵּד לְבָבִי לִירְאָה שִׁמְךָ : 12 אֲדֹנָי אֱלֹהֵי בְּכֹל־לְבָבִי וְאֶכְבְּדָה שִׁמְךָ לְעוֹלָם : 13 כִּי־חָסִידְךָ גָּדוֹל עָלַי וְהִצַּלְתָּ נַפְשִׁי מִשָּׂאוֹל תַּחֲתִיתָ : 14 אֱלֹהִים אֲדָרִים קָמוּ־עָלַי וְעַתָּה עֲרִיצִים בְּקִשְׁוֹ נַפְשִׁי וְלֹא שָׁמַדְךָ לְיַגְדָּם : 15 וְאַתָּה</p>
<p>⁸ There is ^ano one like You among the gods, O Lord, Nor are there any works ^blike Yours.</p>	<p>יְבוֹאוּ וַיִּשְׁתַּחֲוּוּ לְפָנֶיךָ אֲדֹנָי וַיִּכְבְּדוּ לְשִׁמְךָ : 10 כִּי־גָדוֹל אַתָּה וְעָשִׂיתָ נִפְלְאוֹת אַתָּה אֱלֹהִים לְבַדְּךָ : 11 הוֹרַנִי יְהוָה וַדַּרְכְּךָ אֶתְהַלֵּךְ בְּאַמְתָּךָ יַתֵּד לְבָבִי לִירְאָה שִׁמְךָ : 12 אֲדֹנָי אֱלֹהֵי בְּכֹל־לְבָבִי וְאֶכְבְּדָה שִׁמְךָ לְעוֹלָם : 13 כִּי־חָסִידְךָ גָּדוֹל עָלַי וְהִצַּלְתָּ נַפְשִׁי מִשָּׂאוֹל תַּחֲתִיתָ : 14 אֱלֹהִים אֲדָרִים קָמוּ־עָלַי וְעַתָּה עֲרִיצִים בְּקִשְׁוֹ נַפְשִׁי וְלֹא שָׁמַדְךָ לְיַגְדָּם : 15 וְאַתָּה</p>
<p>⁹ "All nations whom You have made shall come and worship before You, O Lord, And they shall glorify Your name.</p>	<p>יְבוֹאוּ וַיִּשְׁתַּחֲוּוּ לְפָנֶיךָ אֲדֹנָי וַיִּכְבְּדוּ לְשִׁמְךָ : 10 כִּי־גָדוֹל אַתָּה וְעָשִׂיתָ נִפְלְאוֹת אַתָּה אֱלֹהִים לְבַדְּךָ : 11 הוֹרַנִי יְהוָה וַדַּרְכְּךָ אֶתְהַלֵּךְ בְּאַמְתָּךָ יַתֵּד לְבָבִי לִירְאָה שִׁמְךָ : 12 אֲדֹנָי אֱלֹהֵי בְּכֹל־לְבָבִי וְאֶכְבְּדָה שִׁמְךָ לְעוֹלָם : 13 כִּי־חָסִידְךָ גָּדוֹל עָלַי וְהִצַּלְתָּ נַפְשִׁי מִשָּׂאוֹל תַּחֲתִיתָ : 14 אֱלֹהִים אֲדָרִים קָמוּ־עָלַי וְעַתָּה עֲרִיצִים בְּקִשְׁוֹ נַפְשִׁי וְלֹא שָׁמַדְךָ לְיַגְדָּם : 15 וְאַתָּה</p>
<p>¹⁰ For You are ^agreat and ^bdo ¹wondrous deeds;</p>	<p>יְבוֹאוּ וַיִּשְׁתַּחֲוּוּ לְפָנֶיךָ אֲדֹנָי וַיִּכְבְּדוּ לְשִׁמְךָ : 10 כִּי־גָדוֹל אַתָּה וְעָשִׂיתָ נִפְלְאוֹת אַתָּה אֱלֹהִים לְבַדְּךָ : 11 הוֹרַנִי יְהוָה וַדַּרְכְּךָ אֶתְהַלֵּךְ בְּאַמְתָּךָ יַתֵּד לְבָבִי לִירְאָה שִׁמְךָ : 12 אֲדֹנָי אֱלֹהֵי בְּכֹל־לְבָבִי וְאֶכְבְּדָה שִׁמְךָ לְעוֹלָם : 13 כִּי־חָסִידְךָ גָּדוֹל עָלַי וְהִצַּלְתָּ נַפְשִׁי מִשָּׂאוֹל תַּחֲתִיתָ : 14 אֱלֹהִים אֲדָרִים קָמוּ־עָלַי וְעַתָּה עֲרִיצִים בְּקִשְׁוֹ נַפְשִׁי וְלֹא שָׁמַדְךָ לְיַגְדָּם : 15 וְאַתָּה</p>

<p>You alone are God.</p> <p>Psa. 86:11 "Teach me Your way, O LORD; I will walk in Your truth; ^bUnite my heart to fear Your name. ¹² I will ^agive thanks to You, O Lord my God, with all my heart, And will glorify Your name forever. ¹³ For Your lovingkindness toward me is great, And You have ^adelivered my soul from the ¹depths of ²Sheol.</p> <p>Psa. 86:14 O God, arrogant men have ^arisen up against me, And ¹a band of violent men have sought my ²life, And they have not set You before them. ¹⁵ But You, O Lord, are a God ^amerciful and gracious, Slow to anger and abundant in lovingkindness and ¹truth. ¹⁶ ^aTurn to me, and be gracious to me; Oh ^bgrant Your strength to Your servant, And save the son of Your handmaid. ¹⁷ ^aShow me a sign for good, That those who hate me may ^bsee <i>it</i> and be ashamed, Because You, O LORD, have helped me and comforted me.</p>	<p>אֲדַנִּי אֶל־רַחֲמוֹם וְתַנְנִין אֶרְדָּךְ אֲפִים וְרַב־תְּסֹד וְאַמֶּת : ¹⁶ פְּנֵה אֵלַי וְתַנְנִי תְנֵה־עֵזֶךָ לְעַבְדְּךָ וְהוֹשִׁיעָה לְבִן־אִמְתֶּךָ : ¹⁷ עֲשֵׂה־עִמִּי אוֹת לְטוֹבָה וְיִרְאוּ שְׂנְאֵי וַיִּבְשׂוּ כִי־ אָתָּה יְהוָה עֲזַרְתָּנִי וְנִחַמְתָּנִי :</p>
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References

Psalm 86:1

^aPs 17:6; 31:2; 71:2

^bPs 40:17; 70:5

Psalm 86:2

¹Or *life*

^aPs 25:20

^bPs 4:3; 50:5

^cPs 25:2; 31:14; 56:4

Psalm 86:3

^aPs 4:1; 57:1

^bPs 25:5; 88:9

Psalm 86:4

^aPs 25:1; 143:8

Psalm 86:5

^aPs 25:8

^bPs 130:4

^cEx 34:6; Neh 9:17; Ps 103:8; 145:8; Joel 2:13; Jon 4:2

Psalm 86:6

^aPs 55:1

Psalm 86:7

^aPs 50:15; 77:2

^bPs 17:6

Psalm 86:8

^aEx 15:11; 2 Sam 7:22; 1 Kin 8:23; Ps 89:6; Jer 10:6

^bDeut 3:24

Psalm 86:9

^aPs 22:27; 66:4; Is 66:23; Rev 15:4

Psalm 86:10

¹Or *miracles*

^aPs 77:13

^bEx 15:11; Ps 72:18; 77:14; 136:4

^cDeut 6:4; 32:39; Ps 83:18; Is 37:16; 44:6, 8; Mark 12:29; 1 Cor 8:4

Psalm 86:11

^aPs 25:5

^bJer 32:39

Psalm 86:12

^aPs 111:1

Psalm 86:13

¹Lit *lowest Sheol*

²I.e. the nether world

^aPs 30:3

Psalm 86:14

¹Or *an assembly*

²Lit *soul*

^aPs 54:3

Psalm 86:15

¹Or *faithfulness*

^aPs 86:5

Psalm 86:16

^aPs 25:16

^bPs 68:35

^cPs 116:16

Psalm 86:17

^aJudg 6:17; Ps 119:122

^bPs 112:10

^cPs 118:13

Targum

Psa. 86:1 A prayer that David prayed. Incline, O LORD, your ear; answer me, for I am poor and needy. ² Protect my soul, for I am pious; redeem your servant – you, O my God – for I do put my trust in you. ³ Have mercy on me, O LORD, for I will pray in your presence all the day. ⁴ Gladden the soul of your servant, for to you, O LORD, will I lift up my soul in prayer. ⁵ For you are the LORD, good to the righteous and forgiving to those who turn to his Torah, and multiplying favor to all who pray in your presence. ⁶ Hear, O LORD, my prayer; and accept the voice of my supplications. ⁷ On the day of my distress, I will call to you, for you answer me. ⁸ There is none besides you among the angels on high, O LORD, and there is nothing like your deeds. ⁹ All the Gentiles you have made shall come and bow down before you, O LORD; and they shall give glory to your name. ¹⁰ For you are great, O God, and you do wonders – you alone are God. ¹¹ Teach me, O LORD, your ways; I will walk in your truth; unify my heart to fear your name. ¹² I will give thanks in your presence, O LORD my God, with all my heart; and I will glorify your name forever. ¹³ For your goodness towards me is great; and you have delivered my soul from lowest Sheol. ¹⁴ O God, arrogant men have risen against me, and mighty men have sought my soul; and they have not kept you in front of them. ¹⁵ And you, O LORD, are a God compassionate and merciful, putting away anger, and showing much favor and truth. ¹⁶ Turn unto me and pity me; give your strength to your servant, and redeem the son of your handmaiden. ¹⁷ Perform for me a miracle for good; when my son Solomon shall bring the ark into the sanctuary, let the gates be opened on my account and my enemies will see that you have forgiven me, and they will be ashamed and confess; for you are the LORD, you have helped me and comforted me.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm describes the essential purpose of prayer. It is not a call for the LORD's assistance but the understanding that prayer makes your soul feel closer to the LORD.

Superscript and verse one

This is not a specific prayer of David. However, because of the accentuation, it is a general prayer of broad significance. All of the Psalms that pertain to a particular person's life should be viewed as being for the entire nation of Israel.

תְּפִלָּה (t'pheela) means "prayer." This word does not correspond to a "prayer," according to the sages. It is generally understood to be a plea or a request. It signifies an exercise for a person's inner self, which can be penetrated by acknowledging certain truths.

A prayer. By David. Incline Your ear, O LORD, answer me, for I am poor and defenseless.

Verse eight

The human soul needs to strive to be as near to the LORD as possible. This verse shows that pure monotheism had not been achieved by the surrounding nations and, to some degree, in Israel. She knew that there was one God who created Heaven and Earth. This was their God. However, at the point in history when this Psalm was written, the concept of one God was not quite in place yet.

There is none like You among the gods, O my Master, and none like Your creations.

Notes on this Psalm

The Psalmist cries out to the LORD and he/she strives to get closer spiritually. Verse eight also indicates that the Psalmist was concerned that his/her soul could be influenced by pagan gods. The Psalmist pleads with the LORD to help him/her to avoid that possibility. Even today people can be taken away from the LORD by the culture of society. People have different gods, like money, and power. When these gods convince a person to worship it then they give up their spiritual connection to the LORD. Hopefully, the person figures out when this happens and returns to the LORD.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

